

ARCHITECTURE

ARCHITECTURAL NOTES IN ENGELBERT KAEMPFER'S MEMOIRS (AZERBAIJAN)

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ENGELBERT KAEMPFER

Abstract

The enormous creative contribution of the German explorer E. Kaempfer, who left numerous travel notes and works on a number of countries he visited, is of great interest. The part of the material concerning his stay in Persia (Iran, South Azerbaijan) (1684-1685) is especially valuable for us. During this rather short period, he collected extensive information about the social system, history, beliefs and customs, and the military organization of the Safavid state. The engravings and narratives by Engelbert Kaempfer form part of a gold fund that provides an opportunity to fill the lacuna on the monuments of architecture and urbanism of medieval Azerbaijan and Iran. Numerous sketches by E. Kaempfer and comments on them are important and necessary for the study of medieval architectural art in Azerbaijan and Iran, including "Meydan-e Shah in Isfahan and the Dawlatkhana," "Khiyaban-i Chaharbagh in Isfahan," "Plan of royal gardens in Gazvin," "Plan of Gazvin" etc. E. Kaempfer published «Amoenitates exoticae...», but most of his unprinted manuscripts, rich in important observations, are preserved in the British Museum.

Keywords: architecture, cities, embassy, memoirs, engraving

The necessity of studying the "travel literature" and in particular the literature of Western Europe, including ambassadors, scientists, travellers, etc. is great, including memoirs, notes, reports, and others, which allows architectural historians in Azerbaijan to enrich information about lost or modified monuments of architecture. It should be noted that memoirs are varied in content, direction, facts and presentation, and that is their exceptional value; this provides an opportunity to see the image that was formed by eyewitnesses hundreds of years ago. Among the authors of the sources are F. Zarre, E. Kaempfer, A. Olearius, A. Jacobsthal, W. Kleis, B. Dorn, G. Barbaro, A. Contarini, A. Philippe, and others. In many of the sources, there is valuable graphic material, which in most cases retains the original appearance of the monuments, thus enhancing their value and uniqueness.

Speaking of famous travellers of the 17th century, it is impossible not to mention the eminent naturalist Dr. Engelbert Kaempfer. Rejecting an illustrious career, he became secretary to a Swedish ambassador on a trip to Russia in 1683. From Russia Engelbert Kaempfer travelled to Iran (then Persia), later joining

the Dutch East India Company, with subsequent travels to India, Japan and other countries.

March 20, 1683, King Charles XI of Sweden equips an Embassy to travel to Iran via Russia in order to establish political and business relations. E. Kaempfer (1651-1716, Lemgo), physician, naturalist, scientist, traveller and individual of outstanding ability, accompanied the Swedish Ambassador Ludvig Fabritius to Russia and on to Iran.

After Moscow, Kazan and Astrakhan, the Embassy arrived via the Volga River along the Caspian Sea at a key destination - the port city of Niyazabad (Nizovaya), located on the western coast of the Caspian Sea and due to the Volga-Caspian route, "Azerbaijan economy and trade experienced a tangible boost throughout the century" [2, p. 25]. The city of Niyazabad was the first port visited by Russian and Western European merchants, it was a place of lively trade, there was "the noblest trade, it ... consisted of raw silk..." [3, p. 37]. The Embassy then travelled by caravan through the ancient Azerbaijani towns of Aresh, Derbent, Shabran, Hajigabul and Shamakhy, and "the favourable geographical location of these towns brought them into line with the transit trade between East and West" [2,

p.25]. However, this was only the beginning of his productive stay in the country, with visits to architectural monuments, with their detailed descriptions and sketches, extremely valuable for architectural historians.

At the very beginning of January 1683, E. Kaempfer travelled to Absheron, where he visited villages near Baku - Balakhana, Ramana, Binagadi, Surakhany (temple of fire-worshippers), the village of Masazir (salt mines), and others. Memoirs about Baku contain many obscure and unknown facts, while others confirm and clarify some of the distortions that occurred later. E. Kaempfer made a picturesque description of medieval Baku (Icheri Sheher) during his stay in 1683, talked about the uniqueness of the city and strategically right choice of its location, its fortification, harbor, sketches of the city, and as noted in the sources Baku panorama was first made by him [1, pp.14,15]. E. Kaempfer described Baku in great detail, although he was particularly fascinated by the complex of the Shirvanshahs' Palace.

E. Kaempfer's journey to South Azerbaijan and Iran included visits to historical cities, sketches of monuments and their description in Ardabil (the religious center of the Middle Ages, the domain of the Safavid dynasty), Qazvin and Isfahan (the capital cities of the Safavid state), and Kashan and others (regional centres), on the Caspian coast in Ashraf (the "second" capital of Shah Abbas I - with a palace complex, hunting grounds), etc. It is precisely the sketches and narratives of eyewitnesses that make them most authentic, primordial, enabling comparative analysis with previously (or later) sketched monuments, clarifying their attribution, etc. Sources note authors who visited and recorded some of them, in particular N. Matrakçı (1532-1555) and Pietro Della Valle (1617-1626).

It was in the splendid 17th century that unique public centers with promenades, gardens and squares, including the titular monumental buildings as well as new types of buildings and constructions, both in the capital centers and in the smaller towns, emerged in the Safavid state. A similar grandiose community centre was successfully implemented in Qazvin, the second capital of the Safavids (1544), and where E. Kaempfer sketched a plan for the central part of the city.

As early as 1590, the centre of the Safavid Empire moved to Isfahan, which became the brilliant capital of Shah Abbas I. Naqsh-e Jahan Square and Khiyaban-i Chahar Bagh formed the main centers of the capital, while Chahar Bagh (1596-1602) was a 4 km long and about 47 m wide thoroughfare [5, p.181]. It stretched southwards into the city, with the formation of Abbasabad and other suburbs, known as "an extended garden with 4 rows of plane trees, with ponds and flower beds, monumental pavilions in gardens of all kinds of shapes..." [5, p.179-181]. The social character of Chahar Bagh was emphasized by the presence of coffee houses here, as well as a sanctuary for Sufi communities in its northern part, stretched between the Dowlat Gate and the Allahverdi Khan Bridge. E. Kaempfer notes that the coffee house owners "spread carpets and mats on the adjoining platforms where people could sit and watch the performances and listen to the poets and

storytellers, and only when it was hot, they moved to cooler premises [5, pp.188, 189]. With the emergence of the problem of the initial buildings, according to E. Kaempfer, "throughout Persia both in the bazaars and on the roads it was possible to see day laborers" busy roasting and grinding coffee beans [5, p.201]: On Naqsh-e Jahan Square, in order to recreate the original look of this part of Chahar Bagh, sketches and narratives should naturally be resorted to [5, pp.180,183,184]. The present condition of Isfahan Chahar Bagh retains many traces of the original elements of this grand main street, including pavilions, coffee houses, etc. In fact, some of its fragments - the madrasa and mosque, as well as the canals, ponds, staircases, fountains and majestic plane trees - are still (mostly) intact.

Kaempfer's schematic plan, sketched in 1680, shows a wide opening in the corner of the madrasa, indicating that the coffee house had been included in the building before it was completed [5, p.181]. The sketches by E. Kaempfer clarify and confirm the earlier presence of the coffee house(s) at this site (in Isfahan - R.A.). The inclusion of the coffee house in the composition of the madrasa is confirmed by the records in Wakf-name, which mention that "the establishment ...was built on the land of the complex ...purchased for the madrasah" [5, p.182]. E. Kaempfer points out that coffee was used in all strata of society in the Safavid state, starting from the shah's court, where it (coffee, R.A.) acquired a very significant role, in particular in the shah's palace there was "qahvehchi-bashi" for making coffee. He notes that there was a coffee kitchen here (in the palace), with storage facilities for storing and roasting it under expert supervision. According to E. Kaempfer, "throughout Persia and in bazaars and on roads it was possible to see day laborers" busy roasting and grinding coffee beans [5, p. 201].

Coffee houses built in many cities of Azerbaijan and Iran (Ganja, Shamakhy, Tabriz, Isfahan, Shiraz) are repeatedly mentioned in sources [6, by Chardin and Çelebi, p. 22] and written about by Western European and Eastern authors. E. Kaempfer noted that "mi'mār-bashī" (Architectus Supremus (chief architect)), represented "tarh" (drawings - R.A.) structures, which were significant not so much for their precise design as for their adherence to the archetype... Craftsmen and artists completed all the elements ...with the many decorative details they learned in their workshops through years of experience" [4, p.18].

Among the many sketches by E. Kaempfer, as well as commentaries on them, should be mentioned "Meydan-i Shah in Isfahan and the royal gardens of Dawlatkhana in the Planographia", "Khiyaban-i Chahar Bagh in Isfahan", "Plan of royal gardens in Gazvin", "Plan of Gazvin." These and other engravings and narratives of the outstanding researcher E. Kaempfer revealed little known or unknown pages in the study of the medieval architectural art of Azerbaijan.

After E. Kaempfer's death, all unpublished manuscripts were acquired by Sir Hans Sloane and brought to England. All the manuscripts by E. Kaempfer are preserved in the British Museum, most of them unpublished.

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